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ABSTRACT BOOK

Free Papers

An aragonite-based scaffold provides superior clinical outcome compared to debridement/microfractures at 24-month follow-up: a multi-center, randomized controlled trial

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Objective: This multicenter, randomized, and controlled trial aimed to compare the outcomes of patients with joint surface lesions (JSLs), with or without concurrent OA, who were treated with an aragonite-based osteochondral implant (Agili-C™, CartiHeal Ltd, Israel) to those treated with arthroscopic debridement/microfractures.

Methods and Materials: A total of 251 subjects meeting specific criteria were enrolled across 26 medical centers. Subjects were randomized in a 2:1 ratio to receive either the implant or debridement/microfracture. Evaluations were conducted at 6, 12, 18, and 24 months using various questionnaires and MRI assessments to measure outcomes.

Results: Both groups had similar demographic characteristics and baseline values. The implant group consistently showed statistically superior outcomes compared to the control group at all follow-up visits. The improvement in the implant group, especially in terms of mean KOOS improvement, was significantly larger than in the control group. Additionally, a higher responder rate and greater defect fill on MRI were observed in the implant group. The failure rate was also lower in the implant group compared to the control group.

Conclusion: The aragonite-based implant demonstrated superior clinical and radiographic outcomes compared to debridement/microfractures at the 24-month evaluation.

Keywords: Agili-C™; aragonite; scaffold; joint surface lesions; microfractures; debridement; RCT